

NOVEL CRACK STOPPER CONCEPT FOR LIGHTWEIGHT FOAM CORED SANDWICH STRUCTURES – EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION, FE-MODELLING AND POTENTIAL FOR USE IN STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A novel crack arresting device has been implemented in foam cored composite sandwich beams panels and tested under both static and fatigue loading conditions. Fatigue crack propagation was induced in the face-core interface of the sandwich panels which met the crack arrester. The effect of the embedded crack arresters was evaluated in terms of the achieved enhancement of the damage tolerance of the tested sandwich beams and panels. Finite element (FE) modelling of the experimental setups was used for predicting propagation rates and direction of the crack growth. The FE model predicts the energy release rate and the mode mixity based on the derived crack surface displacements, utilizing algorithms for the prediction of accelerated fatigue crack growth as well as the strain field evolution in the vicinity of the crack tip on the surface of the sandwich specimens. Finally, a comparison between the experimental results and the numerical simulations has been made to validate the numerical predictions as well as the overall performance of the crack arresters. Based on a linear elastic fracture mechanics approach, the developed FE model was utilized to simulate crack propagation and arrest in foam cored sandwich beam and panel specimens subjected to fatigue loading conditions. The effect of the crack arresters on the fatigue life is analysed, and the predictive results are subsequently compared with the observations from fatigue tests. Overall it was demonstrated that the proposed crack arrester device was indeed capable of deflecting and arresting propagating face-sheet/core interface cracks, and further that the use of embedded crack stoppers is capable of extending the fatigue life very significantly. It was further demonstrated that the developed numerical analysis procedures provide predictions that are in excellent agreement with the experimental observations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures represent a special form of laminated composites comprising stiff and thin face-sheets separated by and bonded to either side of a light and compliant core material. The resulting layered sandwich element or structure displays very high stiffness and strength to weight ratios. Structurally, the face-sheets are responsible for carrying the in-plane stresses and the bending loads, while the core carries the out of plane shear stresses. Sandwich structures are notoriously sensitive to debonding or interfacial cracking of the adhesive bond layers that connect the face-sheets to the core material. When such interface cracks or debonds propagate this may lead to a significant loss of structural integrity, leading to premature structural failure or collapse. Such debonds may be caused by in-service loads such as local/concentrated external loads and impact loads, but may also be induced as defects during the manufacturing process such as e.g. dry spots and resin voids. Ideally face-sheet/core debonds should not occur at all, but since this is impossible to achieve for real industrial scale sandwich structures which may be safety critical, there is a need to develop and introduce design methodologies able to take account of the existence of such face-sheet/core interface debonds. Furthermore, and more importantly, there is a great need for the development of methodologies and

design features that enable the mitigation of the effects of propagating interface cracks as described. This has led to an increased interest in the interfacial debond behaviour of sandwich structures, which again has led to several research studies adopting both analytical/numerical and experimental approaches [1-5].

This paper presents an overview of recent research into a novel interface crack stopper device (a peel stopper) [6-8], see Figures 1 and 2. A numerical analysis methodology based on fracture mechanics and utilising the so-called Crack Surface Displacement Extrapolation method (CSDE) in combination with the cycle jump technique, see [8], is used to simulate interface crack propagation in foam cored sandwich beams with embedded interface crack devices (hereinafter referred to as peel stoppers) subjected to fatigue loading conditions. The emphasis is to investigate the effect of the embedded peel stopper, considering the conditions under which crack propagation, crack deflection as well as crack arrest can occur. The numerical results are correlated with and compared against the results of a recent experimental study [7].

The aim is to demonstrate that numerical simulations can be used to assess and predict the behaviour of embedded peel stoppers and their effect on the fatigue life of sandwich structures. The peel stopper elements proposed in this work are based on the concept proposed in [4], but modified to enhance the crack deflection and arresting capabilities [5]. The numerical predictions are compared with the experimentally observed crack propagation and fatigue behaviour reported in [7]. Crack propagation and crack arrest are modelled based on a modification of Paris' law, while the post crack arrest behaviour is predicted based on fatigue data (S-N curve) for the sandwich foam core material.

Figure 1. Novel peel stopper - shape and material alignment [5-7].

Figure 2: Crack stopper embedded in GFRP/foam core sandwich panel.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

The novel peel stopper manufactured from pre-moulded Polyurethane (PU) resin [23], Figure 1, was implemented in foam cored sandwich beam specimens subjected to fatigue loading conditions using the Sandwich Tear Test (STT) test setup, Figure 3. The sandwich specimens consisted of identical glass fibre reinforced (GFRP) face-sheets and a PVC foam core material (Divinycell[®] grade H100 with a density of 100 kg/m³ from DIAB), and a total of four specimens were tested.

Figure 3. Sandwich Tear Test (STT) specimen dimensions and test setup.

The STT specimens were loaded in load controlled fatigue at two different loading amplitudes; the first driving the crack propagation along the face-sheet/core interface until the peel stopper tip is reached, referred as load sequence A, and the second higher loading amplitude imposed to propagate the crack along the PU (peel stopper)/foam interface until the crack arrest point is reached, referred to as load sequence B. The peel stopper successfully deflected the propagating face-sheet/core debond crack along the interface between the crack stopper and the core. The crack was arrested for a long period of load cycles, after which a new crack initiated on the back side of the peel stopper due to local stress concentrations in the core. The observed crack propagation pattern is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Crack propagation path in STT sandwich beam specimens with embedded crack stoppers.

3 NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF CRACK PROPAGATION

A finite element model has been developed in the commercial FE package ANSYS 15.0. The model is used to identify the crack loading conditions including the energy release rate (ERR) and the mode mixity phase angle as functions of the crack length. To simulate fatigue crack growth in the face-sheet/foam and PU/foam interfaces a re-meshing algorithm is used. Since the crack in all the experiments [22] propagated along the face-sheet/core interface until it reached the peel stopper tip, after which the crack was deflected along the PU/core interface, the debonded area in the FE simulations follows the path of the peel stopper angle (see Figure 5 a). The FE model represents the STT setup without including the unloaded specimen region below the debonded face-sheet in the left side of the specimen, see Figure 5 a. The peel stopper is meshed in the core structure such that it shares nodes with the foam core elements. After crack propagation along the PU/foam interface has occurred the re-meshing allows for the nodes to be separated. In Figure 5 b-d the crack tip elements are shown at different states of crack propagation while in Figure 5 e-g the respective states are shown in the actual specimen.

The FE mesh is created using 8-noded plane strain elements (PLANE 183) with a global element size of 1 mm. The crack tip is meshed using element sizes down to 10 μm at the bi-material interfaces. The face-sheet and foam materials are modelled as orthotropic, while the PU/glass fibre reinforced material of the peel stopper is homogenised and modelled (approximated) as isotropic. Geometric nonlinear behaviour is included in the FE-models to capture the in-plane membrane stresses developed in the face-sheet due large vertical displacements.

The Crack Surface Displacement Extrapolation (CSDE) mode mixity methodology fits classical bi-material interface theory solutions into a FE analysis framework to calculate directly the energy release rate (ERR) and mode mixity of a bi-material crack. A special crack tip mesh is used to extract

the relative nodal displacements behind the crack tip, and then use these to calculate the energy release rate (ERR) and mode mixity.

Figure 5: a) STT finite element model representation; b) and e) Crack propagating at face-sheet/foam interface; c) and f) Crack propagating at the PU/foam interface; d) and g) Crack at the arrest point.

The cycle jump technique is used to simulate fatigue crack growth in combination with the CSDE method. The cycle jump technique is used to reduce the number of simulated cycles in the fatigue analysis. After simulating three or more consecutive loading cycles of crack propagation, the new crack length can be calculated by linear extrapolation for a “safe” number of cycles without running the respective simulations. This allows for saving considerable computation time when simulation of long fatigue sequences with a large number of loading cycles is needed.

The propagation rate of the crack was calculated using the measured ERR [7], the mode mixity and a Paris’ like based on energy release rate amplitude rather than stress intensity amplitude. The input data for Paris’ law were obtained by fatigue experiments conducted on the same bi-material interface configuration as considered in this paper using the Mixed Mode Bending test (MMB). In this study the Paris law parameters were extracted for mode-I dominant crack loading conditions. It is assumed that small variations in mode mixity under general mode I loading do not affect the Paris law curve considerably. Full details of the modelling can be found in [8].

4 COMPARISON BETWEEN FE SIMULATIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL DATA

As shown in Figure 5, the crack propagation and fatigue experiment is modelled in three separate stages:

- Crack propagation along the face-sheet/foam core interface
- Crack propagation along the PU (peel stopper)/foam core interface
- Crack arrest

Figure 6 shows the test machine actuator piston displacement measured for all four STT specimens and the respective FE model predictions corresponding to the load application point on the debonded face sheet plotted against number of cycles for the loading sequences A ($F_{max}=380\text{ N}$) and B ($F_{max}=950\text{ N}$) respectively (corresponding to crack propagation as indicated in Figure 5a and 4b). The first part of the plot (Sequence A) represents the fatigue response of the specimens during propagation

in the face/core interface and the initial stage of the fatigue life of the specimens. The second part (Sequence B) represents the fatigue response after deflection of the crack to the PU/core interface.

Figure 6: Vertical displacement (test machine actuator piston) vs. number of loading cycles; experimental data [1] and FE model predictions.

Figure 6 shows an overall good agreement between the measurements and the predictions for Specimen 2 and 3, but also that a significant variation (scatter) between the measurements for the four sandwich beam specimens exists.

Figure 7 and 8 show the evolution of the ERR and mode mixity phase angle as a function of the crack length (Figure 7) and number of loading cycles (Figure 8). The plots provide a good representation of the characteristic response of the STT sandwich beam specimen behaviour under load controlled fatigue testing. It is observed that the ERR rises considerably with increasing crack length until it reaches a maximum. Past this point the vertical displacements of the debonded face-sheet have become so large compared to its thickness so that the in-plane membrane forces in the face-sheet become dominating and thus affecting the load response. Effectively the induced membrane forces stiffen the face-sheet and specimen response significantly (geometrically nonlinear effect) and consume the majority of the strain energy in the specimen, and consequently reduce the resulting ERR at the crack tip. This is the reason why it was chosen to increase the imposed load at stage b (cf. Figure 4 – corresponding to load Sequence B), when the crack propagates into and along the PU/foam interface. The observed abrupt change in ERR, seen from both the FE results and the experimental observations, is a result of this sudden increase of the imposed load. It is further observed that the ERR decreases again until the crack arrest point is reached.

Figure 7. Energy release rate and mode mixity phase angle vs. Crack length for loading sequences A and B.

Figure 8. Energy release rate and mode mixity phase angle vs. Number of loading cycles for loading sequences A and B.

The mode mixity at the crack tip changes considerably as the crack length increases. This rapid change in mode mixity phase angle means that it is cumbersome to define the crack propagation rate to be expressed by Paris' law, since the crack propagation rate is highly dependent of both the ERR and the mode mixity. A large number of iterations of fatigue experiments are required to define the Paris Law parameters of an interface under a wide range of mode mixity phase angles. Finally, the observed increase of the negative mode-II component at the crack arrest point shows a distinct and very significant tendency of the crack to return to the upper face-sheet/core interface. Under such loading conditions the high fracture toughness of the PU/GFRP peel stopper, achieved by embedding glass fibre reinforcement in the PU material, is essential for the performance of the peel stopper.

The peel stopper itself is not displaying any sign of crack initiation, but a new crack is instead initiated in the core material on the back side of the peel stopper. That makes stage c (cf Figure 5) of the experiment last for a considerably longer period of cycles than stages a and b.

Figure 9: DIC measurements vs. FE analysis results at crack arrest.

The major principal strains in the core material behind the peel stopper are derived from the FE analysis of the sandwich specimen with the crack located at the arrest point, i.e. stage c. Figure 9, shows the field of major principal strains obtained from the DIC measurements for specimens 1-4

during the conducted fatigue tests, and the corresponding field of major principal strains predicted using the FE model. It is observed that the characteristic strain concentration observed in the core material on the back side of the peel stopper in the experiments, is also observed from the FE simulation results. Moreover, the FE model predicts principal strain values that are close to the average of the values measured using DIC. For full details reference is made to [7,8].

4 CONCLUSIONS

A new peel stopper concept for foam cored sandwich structures has been proposed and validated. The research, which is a combined experimental and numerical study, has validated the performance of the new peel stoppers ability to arrest propagating face-sheet/core debond cracks, thus significantly enhancing the fatigue life of the sandwich structure. Full details of the research can be found in [7,8].

The findings of this research are important for future development and application of peel stoppers (crack arrest devices) in more representative real application sandwich structures (like e.g. sandwich panels that may be flat or curved). The proposed modelling methodology can be very useful in achieving this, as it can be used for design evaluation as well as optimisation of the shape and position of peel stoppers embedded into complex sandwich components, sub-structures or larger assemblies.

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